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New records of *Urophora dzieduszyckii* (Diptera: Tephritidae) in Ukraine

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Urophora dzieduszyckii Frauenfeld, 1867, an endangered species listed in the Red Data Book of Ukraine only on the basis of collection material from a single locality in Synkiv (Ternopil Region), was considered the most mysterious European sturgeon species: either an extinct species or a very locally preserved one. It was first found in Podillia and then in Pokuttia, 150 years after its first description based on materials “aus Galizien” (Korneyev et al., 2016 a, b; Korneyev et al., 2019; Shparyk et al., 2021).

Further surveys of the Zbruch River floodplain by the first author (HO) on 10.07.2023 allowed to identify new locations of the forage plant, *Echinops exaltatus*, — on the left bank, within the Khmelnytskyi Region, where about 30 plants grow in one area. More than 40 individuals of *U. dzieduszyckii* were counted on the plants (Figs 1–4).

Further surveys of the floodplain on the right bank of the Zbruch River within the Medobory Reserve on 3 and 5 July 2023 showed that several hundred plants with 2-25 flowering paeonies in each group were growing on already known sites. On most of the plants 1–5 individuals of *U. dzieduszyckii* were observed (UkrBIN, 2023). According to preliminary estimates, this population of *Urophora dzieduszyckii* may number up to a thousand individuals and is comparable in size to the population from Spaska (Chernivtsi Region).

Further studies of this species should provide a more accurate assessment of the intensity of the *Echinops* infestation of plants using non-destructive survey methods and the number of individuals of *U. dzieduszyckii* in the largest habitats within Ukraine.

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Figs 1-4. *Urophora dzieduszyckii*, adult flies on *Echinops exaltatus* plants in Khmelnytskyi Region
Photos by H. Olijar.

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